

THE PROCESS OF TRANSPIRATION IN THE LEAVES OF VARIOUS TREES IN THE KHOREZM REGION OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: It is known that the requirements for trees planted for urban landscaping vary a lot. One of these is their evaporation (transpiration). In this article, the rate of transpiration of ornamental trees planted for landscaping in Khorezm region was determined using scientific experiments.

Keywords: ornamental trees, landscaping, torsion scales, transpiration rate, leaf.

Introduction. As a result of regression due to the extreme heat of the Red and Karakum deserts surrounding Khorezm region, the summer temperature becomes very hot and dry. In order for people to live normally, the humidity should be at least 40-60% and the temperature should be around +30 - + 35°C. Trees play an important role in establishing and maintaining this norm. The leaves of trees have the ability to retain a certain amount of moisture by lowering the ambient temperature by evaporating large amounts of water from themselves to prevent temperature rise and overheating around them and on the surface [1].

The transpiration process that takes place in trees, which are the beauty of our green nature, is important for tree life. It is of theoretical and practical importance to predict that the physical processes in trees also change depending on the growing conditions of the season [2].

Methods. Trees: number of leaves, leaf level index, photosynthetic productivity, water transpiration coefficient, leaves absorb airborne dust and absorb carbon dioxide, noise barrier properties, tree branch shape, condensation of gases and fumes in the upper atmosphere in urban conditions resistance to lack of light, drought, summer heat and heat, pests and diseases, resistance to bushing and shaping, as well as flowering, ripening of fruits and various ethers released from the leaves or body during the summer, pollen does not cause allergic diseases in humans and fruit ripening and indicators such as environmental pollution during spreading are signs of greening. Of these; leaf count, leaf surface index, photosynthetic productivity, transpiration coefficient, leaf absorption and absorption of carbon dioxide in the air, dark and wide shading, start periods of application (vegetation) period and noise barrier properties are considered to be valuable features of greening [3]. For this purpose, experiments were conducted on the territory of Urgench State University in order to study the transpiration rate of trees planted for landscaping in Khorezm region in the laboratory using a weighing scale.

We know that water plays an important role in all physiological and biochemical processes that take place in plant life.

In plants, water is mainly absorbed through the root hairs, the elongation zone of the cell, and rises from the bottom up along the conductive parts (xylem elements). The force that affects the rise of water and water-soluble substances from the bottom to the top is called the root pressure force. The root compressive strength depends on the concentration of substances present in the conductive parts.

Water that passes through the soil through the roots reaches the surface parts of plants - stems, leaves, flowers, fruit bodies and evaporates mainly from the leaf surface.

The evaporation of water from the leaf surface is called transpiration. Transpiration is the process by which water passes from the leaf surface to the intercellular spaces and from there through the leaf opening to the atmosphere. Water moves along the plant body in the direction of the water potential gradient (Ψ N2O). Water potential is the amount of energy needed for water to move from a thermodynamic point of view. When the water content of a system or cell sap is in equilibrium with the pure water in the external solution, their potential is zero. As the amount of solute in a solution or cell increases, the concentration of water in them decreases (water molecules move away from each other), ie its potential decreases. Therefore, the movement of water, the water potential is more or less the same.

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This means that water enters the cell from the external solution, resulting in an increase in volume. The expansion of the cell volume leads to a tightening of the shell.

The surface environment (atmosphere) where the plants are located is almost unsaturated with water vapor. Therefore, the water potential in it is negative, the need for water is always high.

The swelling power of plants is several times lower than the swelling power of the atmosphere. For example, it has been observed in many experiments that grass is 1 to 15 atmospheres in plants and 30 atmospheres in trees. This means that if the relative humidity of the atmosphere is 90%, it will be 3 to 9 times less than the swelling power (140 atmospheres).

The importance of the transpiration process is as follows.

- a) delivers water and water-soluble substances to the upper organs of the plant;
- b) ensures that the process of photosynthesis continues uninterrupted. This is because the carbon dioxide in the air has to pass through the pores of the leaves. If the leaf axils are closed, carbon dioxide cannot pass into the leaf tissue and the process of photosynthesis slows down sharply. Due to the transpiration process, the leaf openings are open, allowing carbon dioxide to pass into the leaf tissue;

c) due to the fact that the body temperature of the plant is much lower than the external environment, its resistance to strong sunlight increases;

g) the increase in temperature, the movement of substances, respiration, and the availability of water in the plant tissue depend on the intensity of the transpiration process[4];

Results and Discussion. Mathematical analysis of the samples taken from the observation was performed in a computer Excel program according to generally accepted methods of marking trees for the experiment, selection of leaves and determination of repetitions, selection of sample branches, sampling and number and quantity.

The process of transpiration was determined in the leaves of trees *Ulmus uzbekistanica* Drob. (Ulmus.1.N.), *Populus alba* L.(Pop.1.N.), *Cyleditschiatra cantos* L(Cyl.1.N)., *Thuja occidentalis* L.(Thuj.1.N), *Biota orientalis* Endl. (Biota.1.N), *Sophora japonica* (Soph.1.N), *Fraxinus viridis* Machx (Fr.Vir.M.N), *Maclura aurantiaca* Nutt(Mac.1.N.). (Table 1).

Table 1. The process of transpiration in the leaves of trees

Name of the plant	Initial weight of leaf, mg.	Change in the weight of leaf, mg				Total lost water account, mg.	Transpiration rate, mg/10min	Transpiration rate, mg/hour
		2 minutes	4 minutes	6 minutes	8 minutes			
Fr.Vir.M.N.	420	417	414	410	406	413,4	241,8964683	1451,379
Cyl.1.N	80	78	76	74	72	76	1315,789474	7894,737
Mac.1.N	180	175	173	171	170	173,8	575,3739931	3452,244
Thuj.1.N.	257	255	253	251	250	253,2	394,9447077	2369,668
Biota 1.N.	284	280	277	275	274	278	359,7122302	2158,273
Ulmus 1.N.	127	119	115	111	107	115,8	863,5578584	5181,347
Soph.1.N.	321	318	317	315	314	317	315,4574132	1892,744
Pop.1.N	471	465	461	458	455	462	216,4502165	1298,701

Transpiration in the leaves of the trees studied was determined by measuring the torsion balance. Torsion scales can be used to quickly determine the process of transpiration in plants.

Torsion scales are very compact and weigh in mg. The account is very easy to identify. The work was performed based on the method of A.A. Ivanov (1950). This method is carried out by rapidly pulling the leaves using a torsion scale of transpiration intensity.

Figure 1. The transpiration rate of the leaves of trees

Conclusion. The transpiration rate was determined using the plants studied in the experiment. According to this experiment, the initial weight of the plant leaf was first measured. The experiment was performed at 9:00 a.m., after which the change in leaf weight in 2,4,6,8 minutes was measured in torsion scales and determined in mg. Accordingly, their initial weight was determined to be Fr.Vir.M.N. - 420 mg., Cyl.1.N. - 80 mg., Mac.1.N. - 180 mg., Thuj.1.N. - 257 mg., Biota.1.N. - 284 mg., Ulmus.1.N. - 127 mg., Soph.1.N. - 321 mg. and Pop.1.N. - 471 mg. When calculating the total amount of water lost by the leaf after 2,4,6,8 minutes, it was determined to be Fr.Vir.M.N. - 413.4 mg., Cyl.1.N. - 76 mg., Mac.1.N. - 173.8 mg., Thuj.1.N. - 253.2 mg., Biota.1.N. - 278 mg., Ulmus.1.N. - 115.8mg, Soph.1.N. - 317 mg. va Pop.1.N. - 462mg (Figure 1).

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